

Current Status of Feed Additives Sector in Türkiye^A

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Abstract: The feed additives sector plays a crucial role in enhancing animal health and welfare, productivity, product quality, safety, and the overall sustainability in animal production. In recent years, Türkiye's compound feed industry has demonstrated remarkable growth, leading to parallel expansion in the feed additives market. This study aims to examine the current status of the Turkish feed additives sector in the context of global production trends, with a focus on structural growth, market dynamics, and regulatory frameworks. Data on production, import-export capacity, and the progress of the sector in Türkiye were compared with major global producers. Current data indicate that technological innovations, sustainable production practices, and the adoption of modern processing systems have accelerated the growth of the feed additives market both globally and nationally. Moreover, increasing awareness of feed safety, public health, and environmental sustainability continues to drive global demand for sustainable and responsible production. Overall, this paper highlights Türkiye's growing competitiveness in the global feed additives market and provides insights into future development strategies for sustainable sectoral advancement.

Keywords: Feed additives, Animal products, Poultry, Market dynamics, Productivity.

^A The study does not require approval from an ethics committee. The article has been prepared according to research and publication ethics.

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Atıf/Citation: Çelik, A. and Kırca, Ö.F. 2026. Current status of feed additives sector in Türkiye. *Journal of Biological and Environmental Sciences*, 58, 20521919.

Introduction

Animal feed additives are indispensable components of modern livestock nutrition and play a crucial role in improving the efficiency, safety, and sustainability of animal production. These substances are incorporated into animal diets at certain amounts for many reasons, including enhancing nutrient utilization, regulating digestive and metabolic functions, and boosting immunity (Makkar, 2016a). By optimizing feed efficiency and promoting growth performance, feed additives contribute directly to the profitability and sustainability of animal production (Perera and Ravindran, 2025). Usage of feed additives has become particularly widespread in intensive production systems, mainly poultry and dairy cattle nutrition, where the balance between high productivity and animal health has to be carefully maintained during the production period (Wani et al., 2023).

Globally, the development and application of feed additives have evolved in parallel with advances in animal nutrition science, biotechnology, and agricultural production methods. Additives such as amino acids, enzymes, probiotics, organic acids, antioxidants, and vitamins serve diverse functions by improving feed digestibility and nutrient absorption to enhancing animal health and welfare, and product quality (Castillo et al., 2021; Ravindran, 2019). Moreover, these substances help mitigate environmental impacts by reducing nutrient excretion and supporting cleaner, more efficient production practices (Khalid et al., 2020; EFSA, 2022). The growing global demand for high-quality animal-derived food products, coupled with stricter food safety and environmental regulations, has further accelerated innovation and diversification within the feed additives sector (Tixier-Boichard, 2020).

The use of antibiotics as feed additives for growth stimulation purposes, in addition to treatment, in farm animals was banned in 2006, primarily in EU countries and also in Türkiye (EC, 2005). This situation paved the way for the emergence of a new sector in animal nutrition. The adoption of modern feeding strategies, the ban on antibiotics as growth promoters, and the shift toward sustainable production practices have collectively driven the expansion of the feed additives market. These developments have positioned feed additives not only as just a supplementary input but as strategic tools for achieving greater productivity, economic efficiency, and ecological balance in animal husbandry (Makkar, 2016b; Chowdhury et al., 2020).

The aim of this study is to reveal the current state of the feed additives sector in Türkiye and the level of development of the global production structure of the sector. This study has focused on Türkiye's global position in terms of annual feed additive production, import-export values and legal regulations on national and international frame as explained by FAO, 2021.

Classification and Effects of Feed Additives

Feed additives are substances, preparations, and microorganisms that, when added to animal feed or drinking water in specific amounts and proportions according to their needs, increase animal productivity and the value of animal products, improve animal welfare, support the digestive system, and meet the animal's nutritional requirements. Beyond these purposes, feed additives have a very wide range of uses, including as toxin binders in feed and for environmental protection purposes. Table 1 lists the additives used in animal nutrition according to their intended use.

Table 1. Grouping of feed additives according to their intended use (Kırkpınar, 2017)

Classification	Additives
Technological Feed Additives	Antioxidants Preservatives Preservatives Emulsifiers and Stabilizers Binders, Anticaking Agents, and Coagulators Acidity Regulators Gel Agents Contamination Preservatives Silage Additives
Sensory Additives	Colorants Aromatics and Appetite Enhancers
Nutritional Additives	Vitamins, Provitamins, and Other Chemical Substances with Similar Effects Trace Elements (calcium, phosphorus, zinc etc.) Amino Acids, Salts and Analogs of Amino Acids Urea and Its Derivatives
Zootechnical Additives	Digestive Regulators Gut Flora Stabilizers (Enzymes, Probiotics, Prebiotics) Organic Acids Herbal Extracts Additives That Positively Affect the Environment Other Zootechnical Additives (Buffering Agents, Beta-glucans)
Coccidiostats and Histomonostats	Anticoccidials Histomonostats

According to Table 1, feed additives are classified into five main groups based on their purpose of use and effects on animal physiology. Technological additives are used to preserve the physical quality of feed, extend shelf life, and ensure a uniform mixture. This group includes antioxidants, preservatives, emulsifiers, stabilizers, and silage additives. Sensory additives aim to enhance feed palatability, stimulate feed intake, and improve product quality, including colorants, flavoring agents, and appetite stimulants. Nutritional additives provide essential nutrients that support animal health and productivity, such as vitamins, minerals, amino acids, and urea derivatives. Zootechnical additives positively affect digestion and metabolism, improving animal performance through the use of probiotics, enzymes, organic acids, and plant extracts. Finally, coccidiostats and histomonostats are used to prevent and control parasitic diseases, particularly in poultry. This classification demonstrates the broad and multifaceted role of feed additives in enhancing both animal health and feed quality. The purposes of feed additives are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Purposes of use of feed additives (Yıldız, 2025)

Additive Type	Primary Function	Effect / Benefit on Animals
Amino Acids	It contributes to protein synthesis and balances missing amino acids.	It increases growth, muscle development and feed utilization.
Vitamins and Minerals	It takes part in basic physiological and metabolic processes.	It strengthens the immune system and supports reproduction, bone and tissue development.
Enzymes	It helps break down complex carbohydrates, proteins and fats.	It increases digestibility, ensures maximum nutrient utilization from feed, and reduces environmental waste.
Probiotics and Prebiotics	It regulates the intestinal microbiota and supports the proliferation of beneficial bacteria.	It facilitates digestion, increases immune resistance, and reduces the risk of disease.
Antioxidants	It prevents oxidation and preserves feed and product quality.	It neutralizes free radicals, extends shelf life, and provides cellular protection.
Organic Acids	It lowers intestinal pH and prevents the proliferation of harmful bacteria.	It protects intestinal health, supports digestion and increases feed safety.
Mycotoxin Binders	It binds and neutralizes toxic mold compounds in feed.	It reduces the harmful effects of mycotoxins and protects the liver and immune system.

Feed Additives Market by Animal Species

The global feed additives market is shaped by the nutritional requirements and production systems of different animal species. Poultry, ruminants, and aquaculture constitute the most important segments of the additive sector. Each animal group requires different additives based on their unique physiological requirements, nutrient utilization, and production goals (Table 3).

Table 3. Feed additives used by animal species (Yıldız, 2025)

Animal Type	Commonly Used Feed Additives	Main Purpose / Impact
Poultry	Amino acids, vitamins, minerals, enzymes, probiotics, prebiotics, organic acids	Increase growth rate, improve feed conversion, strengthen immunity, and support antibiotic-free production.
Ruminants	Ionophores, rumen buffers, yeast cultures, probiotics, prebiotics, enzymes, essential oils, vitamins, minerals	Improve rumen function, increase milk yield, reduce methane emissions, and increase feed efficiency.
Aquaculture	Vitamins, minerals, amino acids, fatty acids, enzymes, probiotics, prebiotics	Support growth and immunity, increase feed conversion, and enhance resistance to stress and disease.

Global Production of Feed Additives

The global feed additives market is experiencing steady growth driven by the growing need to increase efficiency in animal production, improve feed utilization, and protect animal health. The market's total market size was \$37.93 billion in 2024, whereas it is expected to reach \$39.80 billion in 2025 and rise to \$53.49 billion by 2032 (Anonymous, 2025a). This growth indicates an expansion trend that is projected to continue with a compound annual growth rate of approximately 4.31% between 2025 and 2032 (Yıldız, 2025).

As seen in Figure 1 and Figure 2, the Asia-Pacific region holds the largest share of the feed additives market. This is attributed to the presence of countries like China and India with strong production capacity in the region, modernization efforts in the feed industry, and increasing demand, particularly from the poultry sector. The regional market was valued at \$14.46 billion in 2024 and is expected to maintain its leading position in the future (Yıldız, 2025).

Figure 1. Market share of main continent in global production of feed additive in 2024 (Yıldız, 2025)

Figure 2. The future perspective for market share of main continent in global production of feed additive by 2030 (Yıldız, 2025)

The global feed additives market is expected to reach the projected figures in 2030, driven by increasing livestock populations, rising meat consumption, and higher income levels (Henchion et al., 2021). The intensification of livestock production systems and the shift toward sustainable and environmentally friendly production practices are further stimulating demand for feed additives (Asif, 2026), while growing awareness of animal health and food safety is strengthening interest in high-quality products (Zheng et al., 2025). In addition, accelerating urbanization, rising disposable incomes, expanding export opportunities for meat products, and increasing demand for animal protein particularly, in developing countries, support the view that the market will continue to expand through productivity gains and the adoption of modern production technologies (Anonymous, 2025b).

Production of Feed Additives

When examined in terms of additive types, amino acids accounted for the largest share of the market in 2024 (Figure 3). This is explained by their role in ensuring optimal animal performance and the formulation flexibility they provide in feed ingredients. Amino acids are expected to maintain their market dominance in the long term.

Figure 3. Economical value (USD) of feed additive as global scale by different additives between 2017-2030 years (Anonymous, 2024a)

On a national scale, the United States is a major producer, producing over 200 million tons of feed annually and boasting over 5,000 feed production facilities (Anonymous 2024b). The country's high production of cattle, pigs, and broilers consistently fuels demand for feed additives. China stands out with its large animal population and rapidly modernizing feed sector, while Brazil, benefiting from its high meat consumption, strong protein export potential, and agricultural technological advancements, is the third-largest player in the global market (Anonymous 2024b). The European market has been negatively impacted in recent years by factors such as avian influenza outbreaks, high raw material costs, and drought (EC, 2022). Despite this, demand for feed additives to maintain animal production performance persists on the continent (Anonymous, 2024b). These data reflect not only the economic size of the global feed additives industry, but also regional production dynamics, technological development level and sectoral resilience.

Feed Additive Production in Türkiye

The compound feed industry in Türkiye has experienced significant growth in recent years, as seen in Figure 4 and the feed additives sector has also developed rapidly in parallel (Anonymous, 2024c). The adoption of modern production techniques aimed at increasing productivity in livestock farming, the increasing emphasis on feed quality, and the widespread adoption of sustainable nutrition approaches are among the primary factors supporting the development of the feed additives sector (Anonymous, 2019). In particular, the use of feed additives targeting protein synthesis, digestive efficiency, and immune function has been shown to contribute to improved animal performance through well-documented biological mechanisms. Previous studies report that exogenous enzymes and probiotics can enhance nutrient digestibility and feed utilization efficiency, thereby supporting protein deposition and growth performance (Choct, 2006; Bedford and Cowieson, 2020). In addition, functional feed additives such as probiotics and phytogetic compounds have been demonstrated to modulate gut microbiota and stimulate immune responses, leading to improved disease resistance and overall health status (Patterson and Burkholder, 2003; Gadde et al., 2017). These scientifically supported effects translate into measurable economic and production benefits, including improved efficiency, higher productivity, and reduced reliance on therapeutic interventions. This has contributed to the increase in domestic production capacity and the partial reduction of import dependency Figure 5 and Figure 6, and the acceleration of research and development activities in the sector (Anonymous, 2025c). Consequently, the increase in compound feed production has spurred the expansion of the feed additives market and positioned Türkiye as a highly competitive country on a regional scale (Anonymous, 2024d).

Figure 4. Mixed feed additives and premix production quantities in Türkiye (year/tons) (Akalin, 2025)

As shown in Figure 4, a steady increase in the production of feed additives and premixes was observed from 2015 to 2019, followed by fluctuations until 2023. Although the production of licking stones and block baits fluctuated across the years, it generally displayed an upward trend. These findings indicate that Türkiye's feed additives sector has expanded considerably and that livestock enterprises have shown a growing demand for such products.

The feed additives sector in Türkiye is not limited to domestic production; it also plays an important role in foreign trade through its import and export activities. The country's production capacity, global market position, and domestic demand levels vary annually. The following Figure 5 compares the production, import, and export quantities of feed additives between 2021 and 2023.

Figure 5. Production, import and export amount of feed additives in Türkiye (Özkan, 2024)

According to Figure 5, feed additive production remained at a high level throughout these three years, and while there were only minor differences between 2022 and 2023, 2022 was even higher. Imports, on the other hand, declined over time, suggesting a strengthening of domestic production capacity. Although export levels increased in 2022, a decline was observed in 2023. Overall, the data indicate that Türkiye is a significant producer in the feed additives market, although fluctuations in foreign trade continue to occur.

Figure 6. Production, import and export amount of premixes in Türkiye (Özkan, 2024)

As shown in Figure 6, premix production increased substantially in 2023, reaching a notably higher level compared with previous years. Import quantities also rose over time, reflecting the sector's need for greater product diversity. Export levels demonstrated a consistent upward trend across the three years, indicating an improvement in Türkiye's competitive capacity in premix production. These results reveal that the premix sector has significant growth potential in both domestic and international markets.

Factors Supporting Market Growth

The global feed additives market has significant growth potential in the coming years, driven by a combination of factors such as animal health, food safety, and changing consumer trends. The key drivers behind this growth can be summarized as follows (Yıldız, 2025):

- 1. Increasing global protein demand:** The rapid growth in the world's population and rising income levels in developing countries are significantly increasing the demand for animal-based proteins such as meat, milk, and eggs (Smith et al., 2024). This increase necessitates the expansion of animal production, thereby reinforcing the need for effective feed additives to support productivity.
- 2. The expansion of intensive animal production systems:** Increasing protein demand has led to a more intensive and industrialized production system (Luqman et al., 2023). Animal production with range access in alternative systems, especially in poultry production, increases disease risk and stress factors, making feed additives essential for protecting animal health, improving feed utilization, and optimizing production performance.
- 3. Increasing focus on animal nutrition and health:** The importance placed on animal nutrition and health in ensuring sustainable food production is increasing (Keeling et al., 2019). Feed additives play a critical role in maintaining animals' nutritional balance, supporting digestion, and strengthening their immune systems (Perera and Ravindran, 2025). This increased awareness directly increases the demand for additives in the market.
- 4. Food safety and animal welfare expectations:** Consumers are becoming more aware of food safety, animal welfare, and the use of antibiotics (Boer and Aiking, 2023). This encourages the preference for natural or organic additives instead of antibiotics in the production chain. Residue-free, environmentally friendly, and safe feed additives have become a key element in ensuring consumer confidence.
- 5. Changing consumer preferences:** The modern consumer profile is turning to animal products that are not only high-quality but also produced using sustainable and environmentally friendly methods. (Christopher,

2022) This trend is strengthening interest in additives that both reduce environmental impact and enhance the nutritional value of animal products.

6. **Technological innovations and research and development activities:** Ongoing intensive R&D activities in the feed additives sector are enabling the development of new generation products that are more efficient, environmentally friendly, and have specific effects (Areti et al., 2024). These technological advances are supporting market growth by improving both the industry's production efficiency and product quality.
7. **Regulatory legislation and quality standards:** Feed additives are products subject to approval, and their placement on the market and use without official approval are prohibited. Law No. 5996 on Veterinary Services, Plant Health, Food, and Feed, which entered into force in 2010, achieved harmonization with European Union legislation, bringing about significant changes and transformations in food and feed safety (Anonymous, 2010).

Many countries are tightening regulations regarding the use of feed additives to protect animal health, the environment, and food safety. This is driving manufacturers to develop higher- quality, more reliable, and more regulatory-compliant products, giving companies that meet high standards a competitive advantage (Sangshetti et al., 2017).

8. **Economic dynamics:** Fluctuations in feed prices and general economic conditions also impact the feed additives market (Perera and Ravindran, 2025). Manufacturers are seeking solutions to maximize feed efficiency to control costs and increase profitability; this trend is leading to increased demand for certain types of additives.

Factors Limiting Market Growth

While the global feed additives market is expected to grow in the coming years, there are a number of structural, economic, and environmental factors that could limit this potential. Accurately assessing these constraints is crucial for industry stakeholders to effectively manage the market and minimize risks (Said et al., 2025).

1. **Stringent Legislation and Regulatory Restrictions:** The feed additives industry faces increasingly stringent regulations regarding product safety, efficacy, and environmental sustainability (EFSA, 2024). Increased sensitivity to antibiotic resistance, residues in animal products, and environmental pollution risks can lead to restrictions or outright bans on the use of some additives. Furthermore, varying regulations across countries increase compliance costs for manufacturers and complicated commercial processes (Liu et al., 2024).
2. **Fluctuations in Raw Material Prices:** The production of feed additives depends on a variety of raw materials, which can often be affected by the supply-demand balance, climate conditions, and geopolitical developments (Said et al., 2025). Competition with the pharmaceutical and food industries for these raw materials increases cost pressure. Instability in raw material prices increases production costs and impacts final product prices, which can reduce manufacturers' profitability and reduce demand.
3. **High Research and Development Costs and Lengthy Product Development Processes:** Developing new feed additives requires high levels of research investment, scientific testing, and regulatory compliance processes. (Tricarico et al., 2025) These processes are both time- consuming and costly. The lack of a guarantee of success limits the capacity of small-scale enterprises, in particular, to develop innovative products and slows the pace of innovation in the sector.

4. **Consumer Perception and Awareness:** Increasing consumer sensitivity to food safety and animal welfare can lead to negative perceptions of some additives (Nardi et al., 2020). Misconceptions about the harmfulness of chemical or artificial additives can reduce demand for animal products produced with these additives. Furthermore, the shift towards natural and organic additives increases production costs and hinders economies of scale.
5. **Access to Quality Feed and Economic Constraints:** Especially in developing countries, access to quality feed and its affordability can be limited (Balehegn et al., 2020). When producers struggle to meet even basic feed needs, feed additives are often viewed as an "additional cost," slowing market growth.
6. **Competition from Alternative Feeding Strategies:** Alternative strategies such as the use of natural feed ingredients, biotechnological feeding methods, and improved farm management practices can reduce the use of traditional feed additives (Siwach et al., 2025). The widespread adoption of these alternatives indirectly limits the demand for additives.
7. **Economic Recessions and Fluctuations:** Global or regional economic crises reduce consumer spending on animal products, directly affecting feed demand and indirectly affecting feed additive consumption (Brinkman et al., 2010). During periods of economic uncertainty, producers may restrict their spending on feed additives to reduce costs.
8. **Lack of Knowledge and Education:** In some regions, particularly among small and medium-sized farmers, there is insufficient knowledge about the proper use and benefits of feed additives (Perera and Ravindran, 2025). Lack of access to training and advisory services prevents the full assessment of the potential benefits of these products.
9. **Environmental Concerns:** The potential environmental impacts of certain feed additives, for example, the risk of causing food pollution or increasing greenhouse gas emissions, are being closely monitored by both the public and regulatory authorities (Hong et al., 2025). These concerns are creating pressure to develop environmentally friendly alternatives, but this process requires significant investment and a lengthy timeframe.
10. **Growing Trends in Plant-Based Protein:** With increasing health and environmental awareness, consumers are increasingly turning to plant-based protein sources (Ali and Bharali, 2025). This trend could lead to a decrease in demand for animal production and, consequently, feed additives.
11. **Technological Implementation Challenges:** Developing next generation feed additive technologies and integrating them into production processes requires extensive technical knowledge, equipment, and investment. (Perera and Ravindran, 2025). Inadequate technological infrastructure, particularly in developing countries, complicates the implementation of these innovations and limits the overall pace of market development.

Conclusion

The study shows that the feed additives sector has become a crucial component of both global and national feed production systems. Technological advancements, regulatory harmonization, and rising consumer awareness have driven significant transformation across the industry. In Türkiye, steady growth has been supported by modernization, alignment with European standards, and the adoption of sustainable production practices. Greater

emphasis on feed safety, environmental protection, and efficient nutrition has increased the use of environmentally friendly and health-oriented additives. Globally, market expansion is influenced by population growth and urbanization, while regions such as Europe and North America focus strongly on sustainability and traceability. Türkiye has demonstrated strong potential in production capacity and export development, although challenges remain, particularly regarding research and development efforts and dependence on imported raw materials. Enhancing innovation, strengthening cooperation between universities and industry, and promoting the use of local raw material sources will be essential for future progress. If current developments continue, Türkiye is well positioned to become a regional center to produce high-quality, safe, and sustainable feed additives.

Conflict of Interest

The author(s) declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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